

A Stand-Alone Moisture Content Sensor Based on a Loaded Self-Oscillating Antenna

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Abstract—In this work, a portable moisture-content sensor is proposed, based on a self-oscillating microwave antenna loaded by the material under test, for the present case a tree trunk in different hydration states. The operating principle is based on the relationship between the oscillator steady-state regime and its dispersive load, represented by a loaded patch antenna. First, a HEMT-based microwave oscillator with a purely resistive load is designed in the 2.4 GHz range; at the same time, a resonant patch-type antenna is optimized at the oscillator frequency. Then the patch near-field behavior is characterized, in terms of input impedance, both in free space and loaded by the wood in various controlled hydration conditions, over a band spanning the fundamental oscillator frequency and its higher harmonics. The oscillator is then analyzed using the dispersive antenna equivalent impedances, measured at various loading conditions. The self-oscillating antenna behavior is monitored for sensor read-out by a novel approach based on the oscillator’s steady-state dc conditions only. By spanning the dc gate bias tuning range of the oscillator and by monitoring the corresponding driven dc drain current, the moisture content is retrieved. Simulations and measurements show that this relationship is deterministically related to the oscillator steady-state regime variations with the dispersive loading conditions. The proposed solution allows the implementation of a portable sensor with no need for bulky instrumentations for RF spectra monitoring, which are usually adopted for resonator-based microwave sensors.

Keywords— moisture detection, lab-on-a-chip, self-oscillating antenna, microwave sensing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microwave sensors have gained increasing interest in the last few years, due to their high accuracy, low cost, and ease of manufacturing [1], [2]. Thanks to these factors, they are exploited in many fields of applications, such as for medical [3] and permittivity measurements [4], [5]. Most of the solutions are resonance-based sensors, exploiting split-ring resonators (SRRs), complementary split-ring resonators (CSRRs), and substrate-integrated (SIW) cavities [6-8]. The main drawback is the need for laboratory setup, for the sensor read-out. Thus they lack the added value of being stand-alone in such a way that they can be distributed in environments of interest, to perform pervasive monitoring enabling wireless transmission of the sensor data in real time.

Indeed, one of the most compelling application examples of this non-invasive sensing model is in the field of smart agriculture and wood monitoring. Recently, microwave sensing of moisture content and porosity of wood samples [9]

have been presented. However, an external power spectrum analyzer or a VNA, to correctly acquire the data and supply the resonator, is needed.

The present system tries to fill this gap by proposing a stand-alone sensor, whose schematic block diagram is reported in Fig. 1, consisting of a self-oscillating antenna, operating in the 2.4 GHz band, in contact with a tree-trunk for moisture content sensing. The operating principle is based on the nonlinear relationships among the oscillator steady-state regimes and their actual loading and bias conditions. A low-cost microcontroller embedded in the system is foreseen, to perform the sensing measurements by monitoring dc quantities only: while the dc gate bias is tuned over a predicted range, the corresponding dc drain current, which is strictly related to the actual oscillator load, is measured. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, the proposed system is the first one able to convert RF sensor information into dc without the need for additional circuitry, and to enable autonomous onboard measurements.

A detailed design of the self-oscillating antenna is described in the following and the complete sensor architecture is proposed.

Fig. 1. Proposed architecture of the stand-alone microwave sensor. The oscillator output is loaded by the antenna in contact with the trunk sample, device-under-test (DUT). The unique dispersive behavior of the load defines the steady-state oscillatory regime of the self-oscillating loaded antenna, which is retrieved by monitoring the device’s dc operating conditions.

II. RF OSCILLATOR DESIGN AND EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE LOADED ANTENNA

The proposed sensing device is based on the monitoring of the steady-state performance of an RF oscillator, operating in the 2.4 GHz band, with varying frequency-dependent complex

loads, represented by the antenna in contact with a wood sample, subject to increasing moisture contents. This emulates different trunk moisture conditions.

First, the steady-state regime of a single-FET oscillator is designed by the Harmonic-Balance technique [10]. A depletion-mode Pseudomorphic Highly-Electron-Mobility-Transistor (pHEMT), is embedded in a microstrip linear subnetwork consisting of a capacitive feedback stub on the source, and a reactive network on the gate, whose values are derived using a nonlinear/EM co-design technique [11] to define the steady-state oscillatory regimes accounting for the dispersive loads over the harmonics of interest. The substrate is a 0.6-mm thick ROGERS4350B ($\epsilon_r=6.15$), to minimize the losses, and the active device is a depletion-mode HEMT, providing an oscillator frequency band by tuning the gate-source voltage (V_{GS}). In particular, the SAV-331 manufactured by Mini-Circuits has been chosen. The oscillator output microstrip line is the feeding line of an aperture-coupled microstrip antenna, realized on a thicker substrate (a 1.52 mm-thick ISOLA FR408HR ($\epsilon_r=3.68$)).

The oscillator circuit schematic is shown in Fig. 2 (a). First, its output power is optimized on a resistive load, consisting of the resonant input impedance of the stand-alone patch antenna (for the present design 86Ω at 2.38 GHz). The design variables are the microstrip lines widths (w) and lengths (l) and the gate and drain external biases. The predicted maximum output power is about 22.4 mW when the external gate and drain bias voltages are -0.5 V and 2 V, respectively; while the microstrip lines parameters (in mm) are (with reference to Fig. 2 (a)): for MS_1 $w=0.8$, $l=13.3$; for MS_2 $w=1.7$, $l=15.8$; for MS_3 $w=2.2$, $l=12.8$ and for MS_4 $w=0.85$, $l=10$).

Fig. 2. (a) Schematic circuit of the pHEMT-based self-oscillating antenna. The gate reactive network is composed of MS_1 and MS_2 . A capacitive stub (MS_3) is placed at the source pin. The output line/feeding line of the antenna is realized with MS_4 . (b) Measurement setup of the loaded antenna complex impedance.

The antenna loading the oscillator is designed by EM simulation using CST STUDIO. The resulting antenna dimensions are $60 \times 70 \text{ mm}^2$. A measurement campaign of the loaded antenna, that is the antenna in contact with a wood sample (of dimensions $100 \text{ mm} \times 100 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm}$) has been carried out in different moisture content conditions, starting from the ambient humidity condition (dry wood) and for an immersion time in water of the wood sample ranging from $t_1=3$ hours to $t_2=36$ hours. To effectively represent the

loaded antenna for nonlinear simulation of the oscillator, measurements have been carried out over a frequency band covering the fundamental oscillator frequency and its higher harmonics, up to the fourth order (highest harmonic order used for the nonlinear simulations). The antenna, the wood sample, and the measurement setup are shown in Fig. 2 (b).

Figs. 3 report the real and imaginary parts of the antenna input impedance derived from the measurements of the complex reflection coefficient: as expected the loaded resonant antenna significantly deviates from its nominal behavior as the wood sample moisture content increases, resulting not only in a shift of its resonance frequency but also in different trends of the real and reactive parts at the harmonics of interest, over the frequency range of interest.

Fig. 3 (a) to (d): measured real (top) and imaginary (down) parts of the loaded-antenna input impedance in the four loading conditions (purple: vacuum; blue: dry wood; green: wet wood after $t=t_1$; red: wet wood after $t=t_2$) at the first four harmonics.

These measurements are used as the loads of the resulting self-oscillating circuit inside the nonlinear simulation, to build the proof-of-concept of the proposed sensor.

Using a rigorous nonlinear-EM co-simulation, it is possible to accurately predict the oscillator performance when the antenna at the oscillator output port is loaded by the dry DUT (wood sample) or by the increasingly wet DUT. Indeed, its dispersive behavior, not only at the fundamental frequency but also at the higher harmonics, determines both the free-running frequency and the oscillator steady-state performance, in a manner strictly linked to the dispersive load itself.

Over the selected gate-bias tuning range the self-oscillating antenna performance compared with the ones obtained for the reference oscillator with resistive load results in distinctive oscillator steady-states: for example at $V_{GS}=-0.2$ V and $V_{DS}=2$ V, the power to the loads are 7.13 dBm and 4.9 dBm for the dry-wood and the wet-wood (at $t=t_2$) loading conditions, respectively. Furthermore, the loaded antenna impedance reactive part plays a fundamental role in fixing the oscillation frequency, which becomes less dependent on the reactive behavior of the oscillator-embedded linear subnetwork.

To establish the stability of the steady-state oscillating regime [10], a bifurcation analysis is carried out by tuning the gate bias and simultaneously tracking the oscillation output power and frequency variations: a convenient way of effectively describing the circuit state by a single scalar quantity is to use the oscillator output power: Fig. 4 (a) shows this quantity for the oscillator loaded by the fixed resistive load and by the measured complex impedances of the loaded antenna reported in Figs. 3. For the sake of brevity, the bifurcation analysis of the oscillator loaded by the fixed resistive load only is described. Similar considerations can be made for the other four loading conditions.

Fig. 4. (a) Bifurcation diagrams of the self-oscillating antenna as a function of gate-source dc voltage as the tuning parameter, under different antenna loading conditions (black: resistive load; purple: vacuum; blue: dry wood; green: wet wood after $t=t_1$; red: wet wood after $t=t_2$), and (b) corresponding free-running oscillation frequencies.

Thus, concerning the black curves of Figs. 4 it can be concluded that the critical points H1, and H2 are Hopf bifurcations of the dc operating point. The bifurcation analysis shows that the circuit is dc-stable below H1. Thus, since the bifurcation is supercritical at H1 and subcritical at H2, all states belonging to the branch H1-A-H2 are RF-stable [10], [11], including the nominal operating point A. On the contrary, all dc states lying between H1 and H2 are unstable due to a couple of complex-conjugate natural frequencies with positive real parts. This guarantees oscillation build-up when the gate voltage is tuned between -0.8 V and 0 V. For the same tuning parameter, Fig. 4 (b) reports the corresponding oscillation frequency, under the various loading conditions discussed above. Inspection of Fig. 4 (a) confirms that the

tuning range of the self-oscillating antenna is strongly dependent on its actual dispersive load.

III. SENSING THE DUT HUMIDITY CONDITIONS BY MONITORING THE SELF-OSCILLATING ANTENNA PERFORMANCE

The self-oscillating antenna exploitation as a stand-alone moisture content sensor (for all the possible oscillator states - wood sample moisture condition) is obtained by monitoring the dc drain current only, over the gate-bias tuning range where the oscillation takes place, for any possible load under test (see Figs. 4): for the present case this corresponds to V_{GS} ranging from -0.5 V to 0 V. Representative results of the proof-of-concept sensing system are reported in Table I, where, over the V_{GS} tuning range, the actual dc drain currents (I_{DS0}) are monitored for the four oscillator loading conditions under test: for any selected V_{GS} , different and distinguishable I_{DS0} are observed for the oscillator loading conditions under test. In particular, I_{DS0} spans from 67 mA to 204.2 mA in the dry condition, while the wet condition after $t=t_2$ I_{DS0} results in a minimum of 80 mA and a maximum of 213.6 mA.

This confirms that sensing readout by the proposed self-oscillating antenna can be successfully carried out by monitoring the oscillator dc bias conditions only which can be implemented by a low-cost microcontroller with a minimum sensitivity of 0.5 mA.

Monitoring I_{DS0} allows to estimate the power consumption of the proposed system: in the worst case, the maximum I_{DS0} corresponds to the wet wood sample after $t=t_2$, with $V_{GS0}=0$ V and $V_{DS0}=2$ V where the maximum dc power consumed by the self-oscillating antenna is about 430 mW. During the immersion into the water of the wood sample, the I_{DS0} has been continuously monitored and measurements have shown that to detect a 0.5-mA variation of I_{DS0} , a time interval of four hours between two measurements, is a suitable choice. This allows us to conclude that for such time intervals between consecutive sensor readouts getting rid of batteries is possible, and the required power by the self-oscillating antenna may be easily obtained by an RF energy harvester on board of the sensor [12], [13]. This confirms that this solution may be suitable for stand-alone and lab-on-chip applications.

Table I. I_{DS0} values in mA retrieved from the oscillation steady-states in different antenna loading conditions, using V_{GS} as the tuning variable.

V_{GS}	Vacuum	Dry	Wet ($t=t_1$)	Wet ($t=t_2$)
0 V	203.3	204.2	207	213.6
-0.1 V	177.6	178.5	182.2	189.6
-0.2 V	149.7	150.6	154	163.4
-0.3 V	120.5	121	126	135.7
-0.4 V	91.3	91.8	96.9	107.4
-0.5 V	64.2	67	69.5	80

IV. CONCLUSION

A novel approach for evaluating the moisture content in tree trunks is presented, by monitoring the dc bias conditions of a microwave self-oscillating antenna, loaded by the DUT. By observing the dc drain-source current variation of the self-oscillating antenna it is possible to distinguish different moisture conditions in wood samples. Converting RF sensor information into an equivalent dc read-out process allows us to obtain a lightweight and stand-alone sensor, enabling onboard measurements to be wirelessly transmitted in real time. The procedure has been demonstrated by a mixed-mode system consisting of a simulated oscillator loaded by the measured dispersive impedances of a resonant patch antenna in contact with the DUT.

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